

Effect of fluid level on thermal buckling behavior of different reinforced water storage tanks adjacent to pool fire

¹Pourkeramat A.R., ^{2*}Daneshmehr, A.R., ³Aminfar, K., and ⁴Jalili, S.

¹MSc student, School of Mechanical Engineering, University of Tehran, Tehran, Tehran, Iran

²Associate Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering, University of Tehran, Tehran, Tehran, Iran

³MSc, School of Mechanical Engineering, University of Tehran, Tehran, Tehran, Iran

⁴Assistant Professor, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Sahand University of Technology, Tabriz, East Azerbaijan, Iran

*(corresponding author: daneshmehr@ut.ac.ir)

Abstract- Water storage tanks are an indispensable part of firefighting equipment that must be properly designed and manufactured so that they can function properly in forests, factories, and residential complexes. Water containers are highly susceptible to buckling due to their low thickness-to-diameter ratio. Hence, in the case of an adjacent fire, heat can lead to buckling and eventually destroy the reservoir. In this study, the buckling behavior of water storage tanks in the vicinity of pool fire has been investigated. Geometrically and Materially Non-linear Analysis (GMNA) has been used in this research by applying the Arc-length method in Abaqus. The water level in the tank strongly influenced the critical buckling temperature as well as the buckling mode shapes of the structure. Therefore, to prevent the early destruction of the storage tanks, two kinds of horizontal and vertical stiffeners have been applied. Also, experimental data from previous research have been used to validate the numerical analysis. The results showed that significant temperature variations occur at the fluid surface resulting in buckling above the liquid level. Accordingly, the critical buckling temperature of the semi-full tank was 3.5 times larger than the empty tank. Furthermore, horizontal stiffeners were observed to be more effective than vertical ones because of the shape of the buckling modes of each case.

Keywords - Thermal Buckling, Pool Fire, Water Storage Tank, Stiffeners, GMNA, Arc-length Method

I. INTRODUCTION

Fire accidents are among the most critical reasons causing damages to houses, people, and environments. Water storage tanks used in extinguishing systems should be designed and made safely due to their application in fire hazards. These tanks may buckle due to the heat from the surrounding environment. Hence, it is vital to evaluate the response of the structures subjected to fire loading and make an attempt to strengthen it.

The experimental study of thermal buckling of cylindrical thin-walled tanks has long been fascinating to scientists, and there are several papers on the topic such as Ross et al. paper [1]. Recently, through an experimental method, the post-buckling behavior of frames under local and uniform heating has been examined [2]. Moreover, reinforcing cylindrical shells has attracted significant attention [3-4]. Burgos et al. [5] have studied the effect of fluid level on the post-buckling behavior of a horizontal reservoir. The most comprehensive research in this area can be found in Liu's thesis [5] in which the buckling of storage tanks under thermal load induced by fire is investigated with several parametric studies.

In this study, the effects of fluid level and reinforcements on buckling response of thin cylindrical storage tanks

subjected to thermal loading, by applying the Arc-length method in Abaqus, were investigated.

II. METHODOLOGY

Model Validation

To validate the numerical simulation, experimental results obtained by Ehrhart et al. [2] were chosen (Fig. 1). Several rectangular Aluminum panels were subjected to uniform heating emitted from a halogen lamp. The data were captured by the stereo 3D digital image correlation and forward-looking infrared cameras. Given the clamped boundary condition and aspect ratio of the panels, primarily mode 3 or mode 4 post-buckled shapes were expected to happen. Depending on the initial shapes of the panels, this anticipated response would likely be characterized by two mirror-image shapes (positive and negative), according to the sign of the displacement toward the camera. As can be seen in Fig. 1, displacements of the center point of plates in experiments and numerical modeling are in good agreement. The maximum computed error for cases was lesser than 15 percent.

Numerical Modeling

Numerical finite element simulation using Abaqus has been used for studying geometrically and materially nonlinear

analysis (GMNA) with the assistance of the Arc-length method. It was assumed that the structure is made of steel 250, and the material properties are temperature-dependent. The diameter and height of the storage were 20m. Shell and roof thicknesses were 0.01m and 0.1m, respectively. The initial temperature of the tank and ambient temperature were 0 degrees Celsius. The bottom surface of the structure was fixed, and the influence of gravity has been taken into account. The diameter and height of the pool-fire were 20m as well. For simulation, the conditions stated in Reference [6] were used.

Fig. 1. Comparison of the center point's displacement of the buckled plate in (a) mode-3 positive (b) mode-3 negative (c) mode-4 positive (d) mode-4 negative

If the diameters of pool-fire and storage tank are equal, the temperature distribution of a shell can be defined using the half-cosine equation obtained from [6] in Eqn (1):

$$T_{\theta} = \begin{cases} (T_{0m} - T_{0a})\cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{\theta_0}\right) & \text{if } |\theta| \leq \theta_0 \\ 0 & \text{if } |\theta| > \theta_0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where, T_{0m} and T_{0a} are the temperature of the most heated meridian and the ambient temperature, respectively. Also, θ and θ_0 are the circumferential coordinate and the critical angle that defines the heated zone, respectively.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results showed that, if the tank is filled with water, a notable temperature gradient occurs in shell boundaries at the fluid surface location, resulting in large deformation of the storage tank just above the liquid surface. Increasing the fluid level in the target storage tank increases the critical buckling temperature. A particular comparison conducted in Fig. 2 between semi-full tanks.

Fig. 2. The effect of liquid level on the buckling temperature of the structure

Vertical and horizontal reinforcement (VR and HR) with 0.15m width have been used to improve the structure's

mechanical performances. The comparison between each case can be seen in Fig. 3.

Based on the loading configuration and buckling mode shapes, horizontal stiffeners keep the growth of structural damage in the circumference and alter the global buckling into local ones, as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. The effect of reinforcement on the critical buckling temperature

Fig. 4. The effect of reinforcement on buckling in (a) HR in the empty tank (b) VR in the empty tank (c) HR in the half-empty tank (d) VR in the half-empty tank

IV. CONCLUSION

The height of the fluid significantly increases the critical buckling temperature and postpones the buckling of the structure. The presence of reinforcements often prevents the fracture from spreading to the whole structure. HR versus VR has a more significant effect on localizing fractures, subsequently increasing the critical buckling temperature.

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